

EDUCATIONAL PLANNING DESIGN MODEL IN MADRASAH IBTIDAIYAH (CASE STUDY AT MI PERMATA BANGSA BANDUNG)

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Abstrak

Madrasah Ibtidaiyah as a formal educational institution in Indonesia requires an educational planning design model so that it can suit local needs but is also synergistic with national programs and global developments. This research seeks to obtain a design model for madrasa education planning by conducting qualitative research using a case study method at one of the Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (MI) in the city of Bandung. The research was conducted at MI Permata Bangsa Bandung by focusing on the management stages of planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating. The research results show that MI Permata Bangsa has an educational planning design model using the SWOT approach. This model has been implemented and is in accordance with the needs of the madrasah so that it can meet local needs and can synergize with national education developments and global paradigm changes.

Keywords: Design Model, Educational Planning, SWOT Approach.

INTRODUCTION

Madrasah Ibtidaiyah is a form of formal education under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. This madrasah has an important role in providing educational services and developing Indonesia's young generation to achieve National Education goals. The aim of National Education in accordance with Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 is to create education that is based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, which also recognizes religious values, Indonesian National culture, and responses to current developments.

To achieve this national education goal, there needs to be close cooperation between all educational components and government institutions. In addition, it is important to ensure that educational opportunities are available equally, and to improve the quality and relevance of educational management so that it can face changes that occur at the local, national and global levels. Therefore, planned, directed and sustainable educational renewal efforts are needed. Madrasah Ibtidaiyah as an educational institution must have a strategic plan so that it becomes an inseparable part of the national education program. Madrasahs must of course act locally, according to the needs of their environmental context, but they must also have a national and global perspective so that the

implementation of their strategic plans is in accordance with global conditions and developments.

Planning has a central role in directing the goals to be achieved in an organization. With careful and structured planning, work becomes more focused and avoids chaos. Strategic planning, as stated by Ramli (2014), is a leadership instrument and a process that determines the direction and means of achieving organizational goals. The meaning of planning itself is contextual, varying according to the viewpoint and background of the individuals involved. McNamara (2018) explains that strategic planning is determining the direction and means of achieving organizational goals, both as a whole and in its main parts. The process of preparing strategic planning involves three stages, namely diagnosis, planning, and preparation of plan documents, starting from gathering information to formulating measurable plans. It is important to ensure that work plans are aligned with the organization's vision and mission, as suggested by McNamara (2018), so that planned programs and activities can run effectively and in accordance with organizational goals.

In the strategic planning process of organizations, such as madrasas, there are various models that can be chosen to use. It is important to remember that no strategic planning model is perfect, so organizations, including schools, can modify or combine various models to suit their needs. One example is the use of scenario models to identify issues and strategic goals, then using problem-based models to address those problems and achieve goals.

Umar (2008) identified three strategic planning models obtained from strategic management experts, namely the models from Wheelen-Hunger, Fred R David, and Glenn Baseman and Arvind Platak. In these three models, there are main elements of strategic planning, including the vision, mission and philosophy of the organization, analysis of the external and internal environment, analysis of strategic options, long-term targets, functional strategies, as well as program implementation, control and evaluation.

Strategic planning is the process by which an organization determines its strategy and direction, and allocates resources such as capital and labor to achieve that strategy. This strategic plan document includes vision, mission, goals, objectives, strategies, policies, programs and activities that are in accordance with the role and function of the organization.

In the strategic planning process, there are four approaches that can be used to guide strategic thinking, as explained by Pidarta (2005). First, the Guidance Framework approach, in which careful steps are used to analyze the situation and reach appropriate solutions, such as determining long-term goals, identifying environmental factors, and developing appropriate strategic programs. Second, the planning approach, which collects relevant data about problems and situations, then analyzes it to determine the actions that need to be taken. Third, the SWOT approach, which identifies strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges, and formulates strategies based on maximizing strengths and addressing weaknesses. Fourth, the Investigative approach,

which uses research to collect data about educational institutions and situations outside the institution that influence education.

Specifically regarding the SWOT approach, Citraningsih & Wiranata, (2022) stated that SWOT analysis is considered effective in the context of schools that strive to improve the quality of institutions in a sustainable manner. This analysis will provide an objective view of efforts to improve and improve school quality. This is based on the results of an analysis that identifies factors that influence the decline and increase in school performance based on effective indicator measurements (Sodikin & Gumiandari, 2021).

Furthermore, in implementing strategic planning, the role of top management is very important. Top management, which can be the principal or an appointed team, acts as the main catalyst in formulating, directing and monitoring the implementation of the strategy. During implementation, they monitor activities, carry out evaluations, and provide direction, support, and warnings to teachers and other workers. Apart from that, key managers at various levels in the organization also have an important role in supporting the implementation of strategic planning, by providing support and cooperation in achieving the set goals. In all these steps, it is important to maintain togetherness and cooperation between superiors and subordinates as well as all members of the organization to achieve the goals that have been set.

Decentralization of education has introduced a policy of improving the quality of education through tiered management, with the highest accountability at the Madrasah level which has autonomy. This means that the educational community in Madrasahs must be actively involved in efforts to improve the quality of education. All members of the Madrasah community have responsibility for the vision, mission and goals of the Madrasah, and they need to work together in a dynamic network to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process. When the teaching and learning process goes well, the quality of learning outcomes will achieve the vision, mission and goals of the Madrasah.

To realize the vision, mission and goals of Madrasahs, each Madrasah needs to have a detailed strategic management plan, as well as a development program that is carried out every year. This research tries to find a strategic planning model implemented by madrasahs in Indonesia, especially the Bandung area. The research focus of the strategic planning model in question is the aspects: 1) Educational Planning at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Level/Level, 2) Organizing Planning Design, 3) Implementing Educational Planning Design, and 4) Evaluation of Educational Planning Design. It is hoped that the results of this research will be able to provide input to policy makers and implementers to improve the quality of education, especially education in Madrasah.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach to explore an in-depth understanding of educational planning design models at the Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (MI) level. The research method used is a qualitative method, which relies on data collection through observation, interviews and document study. Observations were carried out using the participant observation method, where the researcher was involved in the daily activities of the

informants. Interviews were conducted with madrasa heads, curriculum and teachers to get their views on the design of educational planning at MI Permata Bangsa. Apart from that, document studies are also used to complement data obtained from observations and interviews.

This research was conducted at MI Permata Bangsa, Cibiru Hilir village, Cileunyi District, Bandung Regency. The research subjects chosen were madrasa heads, curriculum and teachers. The research steps include pre-fieldwork, which involves preparing a research design, selecting a location, assessing the situation, selecting and utilizing informants, and preparing data collection instruments. This research relies heavily on the researcher's role as the main instrument in data collection, with a focus on an in-depth understanding of educational planning design at MI Permata Bangsa.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Planning Design Model

The planning design model carried out by MI Permata Bangsa is the SWOT approach. MI carries out SWOT as an effort to obtain a strong foundation in preparing plans.

From the SWOT analysis carried out by MI, the data foundation was obtained as follows: The results of the SWOT analysis carried out by the madrasa include aspects of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats originating from internal and external factors. The strengths of the madrasah include strategic position and location, adequate number of students, programs recognized by the community, teaching staff who have a bachelor's degree and experience, active participation of teachers in KKG activities, habituation of student moral development, good student achievement in the field academic and non-academic, innovative committees, and good collaboration between teachers, committees and parents.

The weaknesses of madrasas involve obstacles related to limited land and limited buildings, inadequate facilities and infrastructure, poor administrative management, teaching staff that are not yet fully qualified, there are teachers who are less proficient in understanding IT, supervision of teacher performance that is not yet optimal, and the location of the madrasa which is still mixed with residents' homes. Opportunities that exist involve the location of madrasas in residential areas, great parental support for schools, high levels of parental trust in madrasas in serving students, increasing middle class growth, developments in communication and information technology (e-learning) in the era of globalization, and assistance from the government to students and teachers.

Threats faced by madrasas include the condition of students' family environments which are not always controlled in terms of good normative values, competition with other superior schools, the influence of students' development and puberty outside school hours, as well as the negative impact of technological developments such as television media, internet, and video games. Apart from the foundation of the plan from the results of the SWOT analysis, MI Permata Bangsa also follows the guidelines provided by the government regarding national education standards. National Education Standards cover

various important aspects of the education system, such as content standards which regulate the adjustment of material to the curriculum, process standards which involve preparing syllabi, designing lesson plans, as well as implementing supervision and evaluation of learning, and graduate competency standards which emphasize achieving academic targets, providing learning. addition, and developing the potential of students. In addition, there are standards for educators and education personnel, which include meeting adequate numbers and qualifications, as well as standards for infrastructure, including equipment, media and learning resource books. Madrasah management is also regulated by standards that emphasize teamwork and professional development support for educators and education staff. Education financing is regulated according to standards, with appropriate financial planning and efforts to obtain additional financial support. Finally, educational assessment standards include academic and non-academic assessment aspects that have an impact on the learning process, involving parents of students in their children's learning process.

2) Organizing Planning Design

In organizing plans, the school organizational structure is very important. The organizational structure at MI Permata Bangsa has clarified the division of tasks based on the authority of personnel in managing and developing the field of school management in accordance with the stated position structure. This allows for coordination and teamwork relationships to be formed based on areas of expertise in managing schools.

Teamwork is an important aspect in organizing a school, and the division of tasks at MI Permata Bangsa is regulated in the work mix of school administrators. Each personnel has responsibility, authority and duties which must be carried out according to a predetermined schedule. Work teams, such as the school development team, the madrasa head team in the KKM, and the subject teacher team in the KKG, all have well-planned work plans.

3) Implementation of Educational Planning Design

In implementing educational planning design, MI Permata Bangsa pays attention to program and financing aspects. In terms of financing, MI Permata Bangsa relies on various funding sources, including government funds such as School Operational Assistance (BOS), monthly infaq fees for superior programs, and school committee fees. Schools have annual budget plans, school activity budgets, and financial reports that are submitted periodically. These funds are managed carefully to support the implementation of learning, procurement of facilities and infrastructure, development of school personnel, and various other activities that support MI Permata Bangsa. In the program aspect, especially the MI Permata Bangsa academic program has adopted a curriculum that covers 15 subjects, combining various curricula from the Ministry of Religion, the Ministry of Education and Culture (2013 Curriculum), and the Tahfidz Curriculum. These fifteen subjects are taught in grades 4 to 6, while grades 1 and 2 have 13 subjects without Arabic and SKI, and grade 3 has 14 subjects without Arabic.

The promotion and admission process for new MI Permata Bangsa students involves publications via electronic and print media as well as organizing activities for RA/TK. New students are selected through administrative selection, academic tests, ability tests, and interviews with parents. The school has developed a good student culture, prioritizes Islamic values, and has a positive work culture among its education staff and educators. Apart from that, the school implements various policies such as school rules, educational calendars, lesson schedules, and policies regarding leave for teaching and educational staff. Cana properly implement various school development activities and programs in accordance with their respective development fields.

4) Evaluation of Educational Planning Design

Strategic evaluation and control is the final step in strategic management carried out by MI Permata Bangsa. This evaluation is carried out by assessing how well MI Permata Bangsa is performing by comparing it with plans that have been made previously. MI Permata Bangsa carries out evaluations through various methods, such as school deliberation forums, observation, supervision and monitoring carried out by school management. Apart from that, evaluation is also included in madrasah self-evaluation and teacher self-evaluation. This evaluation is carried out when the program implementer is implementing the strategy, after the strategy is implemented, and before implementing a new strategy. This helps MI Permata Bangsa to reflect on the strategies we have implemented previously and ensure that MI Permata Bangsa has learned from experience.

Based on the research results, researchers can conclude that MI Permata Bangsa has an established educational planning model. In developing the planning model, MI Permata Bangsa used the SWOT approach (Pidarta, 2005). The SWOT analysis they have carried out involves identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats originating from internal and external factors. Their strengths include strategic position, adequate number of students, recognized programs, highly qualified teaching staff, teacher participation in activities, student achievement, innovative committees, and good cooperation between teachers, committees, and parents. Their weaknesses include limited land and facilities, administrative management that needs to be improved, and teachers who are not yet fully qualified. MI Permata Bangsa also follows national education standards which cover various important aspects, such as content standards, processes, competency of graduates, educators, infrastructure, management, financing and assessment. They have an organizational structure that facilitates coordination and teamwork in school management.

In the process of preparing plans and subsequent actions, what MI Permata Bangsa did appeared to be in accordance with the management theory presented by Wheelen-Hunger (Umar, 2008). This can be seen in the main elements of strategic planning, including the vision, mission and philosophy of the organization, analysis of the external and internal environment, analysis of strategic options, long-term targets, functional strategies, as well as program implementation, control and evaluation. In the implementation phase, they rely on various funding sources, including government funds,

and adopt a curriculum that covers a variety of subjects. Their promotion and new student admission process involves various stages of selection. MI Permata Bangsa has also built a good student culture, prioritizes Islamic values, and has a positive work culture among its education staff and educators.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the Education Planning Design Model carried out by MI Permata Bangsa Bandung uses the SWOT Model. Educational planning carried out by madrasahs pays great attention to the foundation of SWOT data results. Organizing resources to achieve educational plan goals has also been carried out by following certain strategic management. Likewise, program implementation and evaluation have been carried out in accordance with organized strategic management. The planning design pattern or model that has been carried out by MI Permata Bangsa Bandung can be used as a model for managing other madrasahs. MI Permata Bangsa should continue to maintain planning designs that are oriented to the SWOT approach because they have proven to be effective and relevant to national and global development needs. When the government implements an independent curriculum, the approach in developing educational planning models will be able to adapt to these changes.

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